

CARA UPLOAD ARTIKEL DI OJS UNTUK PENGELOLA JURNAL ONLINE

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Untuk mengupload artikel di OJS, ada beberapa langkah, yaitu (1) membuat issue; (2) membuat akun penulis, (3) Upload artikel dengan akun penulis; (4) Menerbitkan artikel.

Setelah membuat akun penulis, pastikan bahwa editor dan reviewer sudah memiliki akun di jurnal anda. Adapun cara membuat akun editor dan reviewer bisa mengikuti langkah-langkah **Cara membuat Akun Penulis** ini. Namun pada langkah 4, **user role** yang dipilih adalah sebagai **Journal editor** atau **reviewer**.

Langkah-langkah ini dibuat untuk pengelola jurnal tingkat pemula, untuk pengelola jurnal tingkat advanced, harap mengikuti **process** yang sudah ditentukan oleh pemerintah.

A. CARA MEMBUAT ISSUE DI OJS

- Klik **login** dan isi **username** serta **password** saudara

Register ULUWIYAH Login

Indonesian EFL Journal
Journal of ELT, Linguistics, and Literature
The International Standard

CURRENT ARCHIVES JOURNAL POLICIES - AUTHORSHIP - REVIEWERSHIP - ANNOUNCEMENTS ABOUT - Search

Home / Login

Make a Submission

Username *
eforeign

Password *
Forgot your password?

Indonesian EFL Journal: Journal of ELT, Linguistics, and Literature

Editorial Teams

ISSN (print) : 2460-0938

- Pilih **Issues**, lalu klik **future issues**

Indonesian EFL Journal: Journal of ELT, Linguistics, an... Tasks 10

English View Site b_jon

Metadata Editorial History Submission Library

Submissions

Issues **Future Issues** new Copyediting Production

Settings

Users & Roles

Tools

Notification
Assign a user to create galley's using the Assign link in the Participants list.

Production Ready Files Search Upload File Schedule For Publication

9441-1 | b_jones, Journal editor, 3. Janpha_Research Article_RE ok.docx Article Text

Participants Assign

Journal editor

- Klik **create issue**

Indonesian EFL Journal: Journal of ELT, Linguistics, an... Tasks 10

English View Site b_jon

Issues

Future Issues Back Issues

Future Issues Create Issue

Issue Items

- Isi Volume, number, year (contoh Volume 1, number 1, year 2019)
Isi title dengan bulan jurnal diterbitkan; Misalnya Juli
Upload cover jurnal anda di **Cover image**
Klik **save**

B. Cara membuat akun Penulis

1. Klik **login** dan isi **username** serta **password** saudara

Make a Submission

Indonesian EFL Journal: Journal of
ELT, Linguistics, and Literature

Editorial Teams

ISSN (print) : 2460-0938
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2. Klik **User and Role**, lalu pilih **user**.

3. Klik **add user**

4. Isi data penulis mulai dari **nama awal, nama akhir, username, email, password**, hilangkan centang di **generate password** dan **change password**, klik **more user detail**, centang **working language**, isikan **Affiliation**, pilih **user role (pilih author)**, lalu klik **Ok**.

5. Klik **User and Role**, lalu pilih **user**, klik **search**, lalu tulis nama penulis yang baru dibuatkan user, lalu klik **search**. Klik tanda **panah kecil** dan klik **Login As**, lalu klik **ok**.

C. Cara mengupload Artikel dengan akun penulis

6. Klik **New Submission**

7. Centang semua kotak yang ada, lalu klik **save and continue**

8. Klik tanda panah kecil, dan pilih **Article Text**, klik **Upload File**, lalu pilih artikel yang ada dalam komputer saudara (format word), lalu klik **continue** (tahap upload file dan menu ini akan aktif jika anda sudah upload article), klik **continue** lagi (tahap Review Details), lalu klik **complete**.

9. Klik save and continue

Indonesian EFL Journal
Journal of EFL, Linguistics, and Literature

Submissions

Submit an Article

1. Start 2. Upload Submission 3. Enter Metadata 4. Confirmation 5. Next Steps

Submission Files

9436-2 janphadpu, Author, 3_Janpha_Research Article_RE.docx (2) Article Text

Save and continue Cancel

10. Isi Judul Artikel dibagian **Title** dengan huruf besar kecil, isikan **Abstract**, isikan kata kunci di **Additional Refinements Keywords** (pisahkan antar kata kunci dengan tekan spasi atau tanda koma di keyboard), isikan **reference**, lalu klik **save and continue**

Indonesian EFL Journal
Journal of EFL, Linguistics, and Literature

Submissions

Submit an Article

1. Start 2. Upload Submission 3. Enter Metadata 4. Confirmation 5. Next Steps

Prefix Title *

Students' Attitudes towards the Class Visit Project

Subtitle

The optional subtitle will appear after a colon (:), following the main title.

Abstract *

The article reports the classroom visit project experienced by 31 Thai university English major students taking a course titled Introduction to English Language Teaching (EN 391) during the first semester of the academic year 2016. The students worked in small groups, contacted the schools asking permission to observe the English classes. They observed the classroom and took notes of what they have seen and learned. They, then, in a small group, wrote a report and took turns sharing their findings in the classroom. After the completion of the project, the students were asked to answer the questionnaires with two open-ended questions addressing the experience and general impressions of the project. Data were analysed using basic descriptive statistics and content analysis. The results showed that the majority of the students had positive attitudes toward the class visit experience. They perceived it as being useful and memorable. The paper also discusses the implications of the findings]

These specifications are based on the Dublin Core metadata set, an international standard used to describe journal content.

Additional Refinements

Keywords

Classroom visits x Attitudes x Experiential learning x Situating cognition x ELT x

References

Zeinivand, T., Azizifar, A., and Gowhary, H. (2015). "The Relationship between Attitude and Speaking Proficiency of Iranian EFL Learners: The Case of Darrehshahr City" in *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*. Vol 199, pp. 240-247.

Zhao, J. (2015). Project-Based Instruction in Teaching Chinese as a Foreign Language Interdisciplinary Perspectives on Human Behavior, 108-127. https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-4666-6603-0_CH007

Save and continue Cancel

11. Klik Finish Submission

Indonesian EFL Journal
Journal of EFL, Linguistics, and Literature

Submissions

Submit an Article

1. Start 2. Upload Submission 3. Enter Metadata 4. Confirmation 5. Next Steps

Your submission has been uploaded and is ready to be sent. You may go back to review and adjust any of the information you have entered before continuing. When you are ready, click "Finish Submission".

Finish Submission Cancel

12. Klik **Ok**

13. Klik nama penulis, lalu **logout as penulis**

D. Cara Menerbitkan artikel dengan akun pengelola

14. Setelah logout sebagai penulis, maka akan muncul jendela seperti ini. Klik **Unassigned**, klik tanda **panah kecil**, lalu klik **view submission**.

15. Klik Assign

16. Pilih **jurnal editor**, klik **search**, pilih salah satu editor dan klik **ok**

17. Klik **Send to Review**

18. Klik **Send to Review**

19. Klik **User and Role**, lalu pilih **user**, klik **search** tulis nama Editor yang dipilih pada langkah 16, lalu klik **search**. Klik tanda **panah kecil** dan klik **Login As**, lalu klik **ok**.

20. Klik **all active**, klik **panah kecil** pada artikel yang akan diterbitkan, klik **view submission**

21. Klik add reviewer

The screenshot shows the 'Review' tab of the submission interface. The 'Review Files' section displays a document titled 'Author, 3. Janpha_Research Article_RE.docx'. The 'Reviewers' section is currently empty, with a red circle highlighting the 'Add Reviewer' button. The 'Participants' section shows the author 'Janpha Thadphoothon'.

22. Pilih salah satu nama, lalu klik select reviewer di bagian bawah, lalu klik add reviewer

The first screenshot shows the 'Locate a Reviewer' modal with a search bar and a table of potential reviewers. The reviewer 'RICK ARRUDA' is selected, and the 'Select Reviewer' button is circled in red. The second screenshot shows the 'Add Reviewer' modal where 'RICK ARRUDA' is selected as the reviewer. The 'Add Reviewer' button at the bottom is also circled in red.

Name	Done	Average Days	Latest	Active	Reviewing Interests
<input type="radio"/> reza Anggriyashati Adara	0	0	--	0	
<input type="radio"/> adrefiza64 Adrefiza - Adrefiza	0	0	--	0	Language Teaching; Linguistics; Pragmatics; and Sociolinguistics.
<input type="radio"/> Yahya Mohammed Al-Marrani	0	0	--	0	Linguistics and literary studies
<input type="radio"/> Jameel Ahmed Alghaberi	0	0	--	0	postcolonial studies, cultural studies, diaspora literature, English literature
<input checked="" type="radio"/> RICK ARRUDA	1	0	2018-04-15	1	

23. Klik untk logout sebagai Journal Editor

The screenshot shows the 'Review' tab of the submission interface. The 'Review Files' section displays a document titled 'Author, 3. Janpha_Research Article_RE.docx'. The 'Reviewers' section shows 'RICK ARRUDA' with a status of 'Overdue' and a response due date of '2018-06-12'. The 'Participants' section shows the author 'Janpha Thadphoothon'. The 'Logout as bJones' button in the top right corner is circled in red.

24. Klik **User and Role**, lalu pilih **user**, klik **search** tulis nama reviewer yang dipilih pada langkah 22, lalu klik **search**. Klik tanda **panah kecil** dan klik **Login As**, lalu klik **ok**.

25. Klik judul yang akan di review

26. Scroll ke bawah, klik **accept review, continue to step #2**, klik **continue to step #3**,

27. Scroll ke bawah, dibagian **recommendation**, pilih **accept submission**, klik **submit review**, lalu klik **ok**

28. Klik untk logout sebagai **reviewer**

29. Klik **User and Role**, lalu pilih **user**, klik **search** tulis nama Editor yang dipilih pada langkah 16, lalu klik **search**. Klik tanda **panah kecil** dan klik **Login As**, lalu klik **ok**. (**Lihat gambar nomor 19**)

30. Klik **all active**, klik **panah kecil** pada artikel yang akan diterbitkan, klik **view submission** (**lihat gambar nomor 20**)

31. Klik **Accept Submission**

32. Centang dibagian **Select review files to share with the author(s)**, lalu klik **Next: select files for copy editing**, lalu klik **Record Editorial Decision**

33. Klik **Send to Production**

34. Klik **Next: Select for files production**, klik record **editorial decision**

35. Klik **schedule for production**

36. Pada kolom **schedule for publication**, pilih volume yang telah dibuat, isikan halamannya, klik **save**

37. Klik **galley**

38. Pada kolom **galley label**, tulis **PDF**, klik **save**

39. Pada kolom **Article Component**, pilih **Article text**
 Upload file article dengan format PDF
 Klik **continue**, klik **continue** lagi, lalu klik **Complete**

40. Pilih Issue, dan klik future issue

41. Klik **panah kecil**, lalu klik **publish**

42. Alhamdulillah Selesai